

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-3-259-IA-2% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	7	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 3 259
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	290.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 290.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/14/2022 4:02:42 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 10:08:55 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.100	1048180	28.74	82075
2	8.986	1047301	28.72	64476
3	10.346	769169	21.09	51763
4	13.387	782259	21.45	40473

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-3-253-IA-2% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	7	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 3 253
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	290.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 290.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/14/2022 4:24:34 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 10:09:59 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.361	10821	0.12	868
2	9.042	8904956	97.80	529504
3	10.646	92839	1.02	5615
4	13.572	97105	1.07	5255